

ECO - FRIENDLY NATURAL COLORS YIELDING FLOWERING PLANTS OF COLLEGE CAMPUS KILA BHAVAN INDORE DISTRICT (M.P.) – A SURVEY REPORT

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INTRODUCTION

Color is one of the elements of nature that made the human living more aesthetic and fascinating in the world. They are supposed to be associated with emotions, human qualities, seasons, festivals and passion in our life .I n India, there are more than 450 plants that can yield bright colors. Natural dyes are environment friendly such , turmeric, the brightest of naturally occurring yellow color is a powerful antiseptic which revitalizes the skin, (R.Siva,2007)*Punicagranatum*L. (Anar)*Lawsoniainermis*L.(henna), and many other common natural color yielding plants(Hussein, 1997)The present study mainly focuses on some important plants having color yielding potential. As many as 25species were screened for colouring. These species belonging to25genera and 18families are presented in this paper. The botanical names, family,vernacular name and parts from which color is obtained and the colours fixed after treating withrecommended mordents.Natural colorants derived from flora and fauna are believed to be safe because of its nontoxic, non-carcinogenic and biodegradable in nature (Cristea&Vilarem, 2003). Different parts of the plants were used for the extraction of dyes such as bark , leaves, flowers, etc and different types of mordents were used for fixing the dye into the fabric.Study of available literature shows that several studies were carried out on natural color yielding plants in the recent past. (A. Rashmi *et al.*, 2004, Debajit and Tiwari 2005, Gour 2008 and Garget *et al.*, 2010) color yielding plants are not properly studied with reference to Madhya Pradesh, (Tiwari and Bharat 2008), (Choudhary and Upadhyay 2011) Present work is undertaken to study the color yielding plants of Sehore district.

STUDY AREA

College is basically a Fort of Holker Emperor .The area of Fort is 52610 Sq. Meter. Holker Emperor constructed it in 1860; it was constructed by cement and lime. The college established in 1963 in the Fort.The study site and surrounding area is rich in flora.Floristic composition is the major morphological characters of the plant community. Thus, a detailed survey of the floristic vegetation was carried out in and around the study site .After survey 25 plants selected for extraction of natural colors .

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Test of natural colors in Plant parts.

1.Squeeze the plant part preferably flowers and leaves between the fingers if color is discharged, it may be a good source of natural color.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

From the observation and results, it can be concluded that during Preliminary survey it was recorded that the college campus rich in vegetation luxuriant growth of trees, under shrub, shrubs and herbs were registered. Diwangi (1980) studied the vegetation of Indore district. From the study area 25 plants recorded as a natural color yielding plants. The plant part flowers and bark dominated as a plant parts from which the brown and yellow natural color obtained. Nowadays most of the natural colors are interested to use natural dye materials in the same ways used for synthetic dyes. Textile dyers must know the chemistry of these natural colors and its Use of suitable binary or ternary mixtures of similar or compatible natural dyes for coloring natural eco-friendly textiles in variety of soothing /uncommon shades with eco-friendly mordants and finishing agents are the most desirable product of the customers for future. Thus with the worldwide concern over the use of eco-friendly and biodegradable materials, the use of natural dyes has undoubtedly once again gained interest and momentum.

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